

THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN INTELLECTUAL CAPITAL, INNOVATIVE WORK BEHAVIOUR, ORGANISATIONAL CULTURE AND KNOWLEDGE MANAGEMENT ON BUSINESS PERFORMANCE

Muhammad Laras Widyanto ¹ and Sri Kurniawati ²

¹ Universitas Mercu Buana, Jakarta, Indonesia. Email: muhammadlaras@mercubuana.ac.id

² Universitas Persada Indonesia YAI, Jakarta, Indonesia. Email: sri.kurniawati@upi-yai.ac.id

DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.13756828](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13756828)

Abstract

In the era of competition in the competitive business industry, companies are required to always innovate to carry out their business activities. This study aims to examine how intellectual capital, innovative work behaviour, organizational culture and knowledge management affect business performance in the context of modern organisations. This research uses quantitative methods with surveys to collect data from employees and business owners. The study found that intellectual capital plays a key role in enhancing a company's competitiveness and innovation capabilities. Innovative work behaviour is proven to encourage the creation of creative solutions and improved operational efficiency. In addition, an organizational culture that supports collaboration and continuous learning contributes to a productive work environment. Knowledge management ensures effective management and utilisation of information for strategic decision-making. The findings suggest that the integration of these four factors significantly improves business performance, providing a solid foundation for companies to achieve competitive advantage and long-term growth.

Keyword: Intellectual Capital, Innovative Work Behaviour, Organizational Culture, Knowledge Management, Business Performance.

INTRODUCTION

Intellectual capital (IC) is an important intangible asset in creating added value for an organization which consists of human capital, structural capital and relational capital. Human capital includes the knowledge, skills, competencies and experience possessed by employees in the organisation. Humans are the most dynamic resources that play a role in innovation and productivity. Structural capital is the organisational infrastructure that supports human capital, including systems, procedures, corporate culture and databases that facilitate the flow of information and knowledge. Relational capital includes external relationships with customers, suppliers, business partners and other external networks that support business growth and sustainability. These three components are interrelated and contribute to an organisation's competitive advantage and long-term performance (Artati, 2017; Sari, 2020; Tamosiuniene et al., 2015).

Innovative work behaviour (IWB) is the actions and processes undertaken by employees in creating, introducing and implementing new ideas that can improve organisational effectiveness and efficiency. This behaviour involves seeking opportunities, developing creative solutions, and applying innovations in daily work. Concrete examples of innovative work behaviours include the development of new products, the improvement of business processes, and the application of new technologies to improve operational performance. These innovative behaviours not only increase productivity but also enable organisations to remain competitive in an ever-changing marketplace (Hadi et al., 2020; Mazidah & Laily, 2020; Vinogradova & Kuvshinov, 2022).

Business performance is a measure of an organisation's success in achieving its goals and objectives through the effective and efficient use of resources. Business performance includes various aspects such as profitability, growth, operational efficiency and customer satisfaction (Darmawan et al., 2023; Paramansyah & SE, 2022; Taouab & Issor, 2019).

In recent years, there has been a significant increase in the number of Micro, Small, and Medium Enterprises (MSMEs) entering the digital ecosystem in Indonesia. The Ministry of Cooperatives and SMEs reported that in 2022, the number of MSMEs participating in this ecosystem reached 20.76 million units, a 26.6% increase compared to the previous year, which had only 16.4 million MSMEs (DataIndonesia.id, 2022). This increase highlights the importance of intellectual capital, innovative work behavior, organizational culture, and knowledge management in driving the business performance of MSMEs in the digital era.

Intellectual capital and innovative work behaviour have a close and significant relationship with firm performance. Intellectual capital provides the foundation of knowledge, skills, and networks necessary to create innovation (Gross-Golacka et al., 2020); (Pigola et al., 2022). When employees are empowered with deep knowledge and supportive systems, they are more likely to exhibit innovative work behaviours, such as developing new products, improving processes, and seeking creative solutions to business challenges (Wang et al., 2014). These innovative behaviours in turn drive improved firm performance through increased operational efficiency, higher customer satisfaction, and the ability to adapt quickly to market changes (Mardikaningsih & Darmawan, 2023). The combination of IC and IWB has a significant impact on business performance, improving productivity, efficiency, and profitability (Chahal & Bakshi, 2014).

Previous studies show that there is a strong relationship between IC and business performance (BP) (Sari, 2020). Research has confirmed that companies with high intellectual capital, such as deep knowledge, technical expertise, and strong relational networks, tend to have better performance in terms of profitability, operational efficiency, and market growth. In addition, various studies also implement creative solutions, significantly contributing to the achievement of business goals, including increased productivity and product innovation (Putriana, 2023; Rochmawati et al., 2023). Some studies even integrate these two concepts, suggesting that synergies between IC and IWB can further improve business performance (Jaradat et al., 2024).

Organizational culture is a set of values, beliefs, norms, and practices that guide members of an organization in their behavior and interactions (Nugroho, 2024). This culture is formed through the organization's history, leadership, vision, mission, and the daily interactions among its members. External factors such as the industry environment and government policies also influence the formation of organizational culture. The impact of a strong organizational culture on employee performance is significant; a positive culture can enhance motivation, job satisfaction, and employee loyalty, ultimately boosting overall productivity and company performance. Additionally, a cohesive organizational culture helps create a strong company identity, improves reputation, and provides a sustainable competitive advantage (Rulianti, 2022).

Knowledge Management is the systematic process of creating, sharing, using, and managing knowledge and information within an organization (Praharsi, 2016). The

importance of knowledge management lies in its ability to leverage the organization's intellectual assets, enhance collective learning, and ensure that critical knowledge is available for decision-making. Effective knowledge management allows an organization to develop innovation by integrating new ideas from various sources, improve operational efficiency through the dissemination of best practices, and enhance responsiveness to market changes by providing relevant and up-to-date information (Sutisna et al., 2024).

The potential relationship between intellectual capital, innovative work behavior, organizational culture, and knowledge management with business performance is closely intertwined and mutually influential. Intellectual capital can drive innovative work behavior if supported by an organizational culture that is conducive and open to change. Effective knowledge management ensures that relevant knowledge and information are well-disseminated throughout the organization, thereby enhancing the ability to innovate and adapt to market changes. Thoroughly investigating this relationship is crucial to understand how each factor contributes to overall business performance and to identify synergies that can be optimized. A holistic approach allows for a deeper understanding of the impact of each factor and how their combination can create a sustainable competitive advantage.

Based on the background described above, the main objective of this research is to understand and measure the influence of intellectual capital, innovative work behavior, organizational culture, and knowledge management on business performance. This study aims to identify the extent to which each of these factors contributes to achieving optimal business performance and how their interactions can create synergies that enhance a company's competitiveness. It is expected that the contribution of this research to the academic literature will enrich the theoretical understanding of the dynamics between intellectual assets and other organizational factors in the context of business performance. From a business practice perspective, the findings of this research are expected to provide practical insights that managers and organizational leaders can use to design effective strategies for knowledge management, fostering innovation, and building a strong organizational culture to improve overall business performance and success.

RESEARCH METHOD

The research methodology used in this study is a quantitative approach with a survey design. The research population consists of entrepreneurs and SMEs operating in Indonesia. The sample will be drawn from this population from May to June 2024. The criteria for respondents include employees or business owners who are directly involved in the operations of SMEs. The sampling technique will be purposive sampling to ensure that respondents meet the specific criteria necessary to accurately address the research questions.

Data will be collected through questionnaires designed to measure five main variables: intellectual capital, innovative work behavior, organizational culture, knowledge management, and business performance. Intellectual capital will be measured using indicators that include aspects such as knowledge, skills, and networks. Innovative work behavior will be assessed through indicators related to creativity and the implementation of new ideas. Business performance will be evaluated based on indicators such as productivity, efficiency, and profitability. Organizational culture will

be measured through various aspects such as shared values, norms, and practices applied within the organization. Meanwhile, knowledge management will be measured using a scale that assesses various dimensions such as knowledge creation, knowledge sharing, and knowledge application within the organizational context. This approach aims to provide a comprehensive understanding of how each of these factors contributes to overall business performance and their interactions in fostering a competitive advantage.

Data analysis will be conducted using multiple linear regression techniques to test the relationships between variables and verify the research hypotheses. This technique will help identify the extent to which intellectual capital, innovative work behavior, organizational culture, and knowledge management influence business performance. The validity and reliability of the questionnaire will be tested to ensure the accuracy and consistency of the data obtained. With this method, the research is expected to provide deep insights into how all of independent variables contribute to the overall improvement of business performance.

Framework

Figure 1: Framework

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

In this study, data analysis is conducted using Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) with a Partial Least Squares (PLS) approach. The SEM-PLS technique is chosen for its ability to handle complex models with latent variables and intricate relationships, and it can work with small to medium sample sizes. The analysis process involves developing a conceptual model, collecting data from respondents, and testing the measurement model to ensure the validity and reliability of the latent variable indicators. Subsequently, the structural model is tested to identify and evaluate the

strength and direction of the relationships between the variables, such as intellectual capital, innovative work behaviour, organisational culture, and knowledge management on business performance. This approach allows the study to provide in-depth insights into how these factors affect overall business performance.

Result

Table 1: Respondent Profile Characteristics

Characteristic	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent	
Gender	Male	60	60	60	60
	Female	40	40	40	100
	Total	100	100	100	
Age	27-42 Years	77	77	77	77
	43-58 Years	23	23	23	100
	Total	100	100	100	
Education	High School	67	67	67	67
	Diploma	5	5	5	72
	Bachelor	26	26	26	98
	Magister	2	2	2	100
	Total	100	100	100	
Position	Owner	66	66	66	66
	Manager	16	16	16	82
	Staff	18	18	18	100
	Total	100	100	100	

Source: Data Processed (2024)

The table above shows that the respondent characteristics exhibit interesting variations. Of the 100 respondents, 60% are male and 40% are female. The majority of respondents fall within the age range of 27 to 42 years, comprising 77% of the total participants, while the remaining 23% are aged between 43 and 58 years. In terms of educational background, most respondents have completed high school (67%), followed by bachelor's degree holders (26%), diploma holders (5%), and master's degree holders (2%). Regarding their positions within the company, the majority are business owners (66%), followed by managers (16%) and staff members (18%). These characteristics provide a comprehensive overview of the demographics and positions of the participants involved in this study and can represent the research results effectively.

Validity and Reliability Test

Validity and reliability tests are two important procedures in quantitative research to ensure that data collection instruments, such as questionnaires or tests, function accurately and consistently. Validity tests assess the extent to which the instrument actually measures what it is supposed to measure, ensuring the relevance of the questions or items in the instrument to the concept under study, so as to provide an accurate picture of the variable being studied. Validity can be tested through various methods, including content, construct, and criterion validity. On the other hand, a reliable instrument will produce stable and consistent results over time, indicating that the tool is free from random error. Reliability is often tested using the Cronbach's Alpha method. Thus, validity and reliability tests together ensure that research instruments produce reliable data that can be used to make valid conclusions.

Table 2: Validity and Reliability Test Result

	Cronbach's Alpha	rho_A	Composite Reliability	Average Variance Extract (AVE)	Description
Intellectual Capital	0.797	0.808	0.880	0.710	Valid and Reliable
Inovative Work Behaviour	0.919	0.922	0.937	0.711	Valid and Reliable
Organizational Culture	0.851	0.855	0.893	0.627	Valid and Reliable
Knowledge Management	0.893	0.901	0.916	0.609	Valid and Reliable
Business Performance	0.908	0.912	0.927	0.645	Valid and Reliable

Source: Data Processed (2024)

The table above shows that each variable has an AVE value of more than 0.5, which indicates that the questionnaire items used are valid. In addition, instrument reliability is tested by looking at the Cronbach Alpha value and composite reliability, both of which must exceed 0.7. Each variable in this study fulfils these criteria. Therefore, the measurement of variables in terms of validity and reliability has been fulfilled, and the research can proceed to the next stage.

Determination Coefficient Test

The coefficient of determination test is a measure in regression analysis that shows how well the regression model can explain variations in the dependent variable based on the independent variable. This test helps researchers understand the strength and relevance of the regression model used, so that they can assess how accurate the predictions or estimates produced by the model are.

Table 3: Determination Coefficient Test Result

	R Square	Adjusted R Square
Business Performance	0.910	0.906

Source: Data Processed (2024)

Based on the Adjusted R Square value of 0.906, it indicates that business performance can be explained by 90.6% through the variables of intellectual capital, innovative work behavior, organizational culture, and knowledge management. The remaining percentage is accounted for by other factors outside the scope of this research.

F Square Test

F square (f^2) is an effect size used in structural path analysis or structural equation modelling (SEM) to assess the effect size of predictors on endogenous variables. It measures the magnitude of the contribution of each predictor to the endogenous variable in the model. The f^2 value is calculated based on the change in the R^2 value when a particular predictor is removed from the model. The f^2 value can be interpreted as follows: $f^2 = 0.02$ indicates a small effect, $f^2 = 0.15$ indicates a medium effect, and $f^2 = 0.35$ indicates a large effect. The use of f^2 helps researchers to understand the relative contribution of each predictor variable in explaining variation in the dependent variable, thereby providing greater insight into the structure of the relationships in the research model.

Table 4: F Square Test Result

	Business Performance	Description
Intellectual Capital	0.071	Small
Inovative Work Behaviour	0.119	Small
Organizational Culture	0.096	Small
Knowledge Management	0.089	Small

Source: Data Processed (2024)

The table above shows that both variables have f-square values that are not significantly different, falling within the small category in terms of their influence on business performance.

Hypothesis Test

Hypothesis testing is a statistical method used to determine whether there is enough evidence in a sample of data to support a hypothesis about the population. The hypothesis testing procedure includes steps such as determining the significance level (alpha), calculating the test statistic, and comparing the p value with the significance level.

Table 5: Hypothesis Test Result

	Original Sample (O)	Average Sample (M)	Standard Deviation (STDEV)	T Statistic (O/STDEV)	P Values	Description
Intellectual Capital -> Business Performance	0.159	0.150	0.064	2.499	0.013	Significant Positive Effect
Inovative Work Behaviour -> Business Performance	0.261	0.245	0.098	2.671	0.008	Significant Positive Effect
Organizational Culture -> Business Performance	0.311	0.310	0.152	2.049	0.041	Significant Positive Effect
Knowledge Management -> Business Performance	0.270	0.296	0.130	2.067	0.039	Significant Positive Effect

Source: Data Processed (2024)

Intellectual capital has a t-value > t-table ($2.499 > 1.984$) with a significance level of 0.013. This indicates that intellectual capital has a positive and significant impact on business performance. Thus, an increase in intellectual capital is associated with improved business performance.

IWB has a t-value > t-table ($2.671 > 1.984$) with a significance level of 0.008. This suggests that innovative work behavior has a positive and significant effect on business performance. Therefore, an increase in IWB leads to enhanced business performance.

Organizational culture has a t-value > t-table ($2.049 > 1.984$) with a significance level of 0.041. This means that organizational culture has a positive and significant impact on business performance. Consequently, an improvement in organizational culture is associated with increased business performance.

Knowledge management has a t-value > t-table (2.067 > 1.984) with a significance level of 0.039. This indicates that KM has a positive and significant influence on business performance. Thus, an increase in KM is correlated with better business performance.

Discussion

The Effect of Intellectual Capital on Business Performance

The test results showed that intellectual capital has a positive and significant effect on business performance. This finding is in line with the study results from (Dewi & Setyowati, 2015); (Aida & Rahmawati, 2015); (Febry, 2018). IC involves three main components: human capital, structural capital, and relational capital. Human capital includes the knowledge, skills and experience of employees who contribute more effectively to achieving company targets. Employees with deep expertise and extensive experience can provide better and innovative solutions, improve work productivity and efficiency, and participate in the development of new products or services.

In addition, structural capital serves to create and maintain processes, systems and cultures that support the utilization of employees' knowledge and skills. Solid infrastructure, such as efficient knowledge management systems and good operational procedures facilitate the dissemination and use of critical information within the organisation. With strong structural capital in place, organizations can ensure that business processes run smoothly and available knowledge is used optimally, directly impacting business performance.

Relational capital which includes the relationships and networks an organization has with external parties such as customers, suppliers and partners also plays a critical part in increasing BP. Extensive networks and good relationships can provide access to resources, market information and business opportunities that are not available if the organization relies solely on its internal capital. Solid relationships with external partners help in accelerating innovation and improving responsiveness to market changes, which ultimately support the achievement of better business performance.

Overall, the three components of IC work synergistically to support business performance. Human capital provides skills and knowledge, structural capital ensures supportive systems and processes, while relational capital strengthens market position and access to external resources. The effective integration of these three elements creates a strong foundation for the achievement of business objectives, improves efficiency and drives innovation which all contribute to optimal and sustainable business performance.

The Effect of Innovative Work Behaviour on Business Performance

The results showed that innovative work behaviour has a positive and significant effect on business performance. This finding is in line with (Cahyaningati et al., 2022); (Hadi et al., 2020); (Elny, 2021); (Deng et al., 2022). IWB suggests staff members to propose new ideas and creative solutions that can improve various aspects of a company's operations. Employees who exhibit innovative behaviour are actively involved in the process of finding and implementing unconventional solutions to overcome challenges and take advantage of opportunities. By introducing new methods and more efficient approaches, they can improve work processes, enhance the quality of products or

services, and optimise the use of resources which ultimately contributes to improving overall business performance.

In addition, innovative work behaviours also contribute to a company's competitive advantage by enabling the organisation to adapt quickly to changing market and industry trends. Employees who innovate constantly help companies to stay relevant and responsive to evolving customer needs. For example, the development of new products that fulfil unmet market needs or process improvements that reduce production time can give a company an advantage over its competitors.

Innovative behaviour also has a positive impact on customer satisfaction and loyalty. Successfully launched innovations usually improve the quality of products or services offered to customers. When companies consistently deliver new solutions that meet or exceed customer expectations, this contributes to increased customer satisfaction and loyalty. High customer satisfaction often leads to better customer retention and improved company reputation, which in turn affects business performance through increased sales and profitability.

Innovative work behaviour can influence business performance through its impact on employee motivation and engagement. Employees who are given the opportunity to innovate often feel more motivated and engaged in their work because they feel valued and have an important role to play in achieving company goals. High motivation and strong engagement usually lead to increased productivity and reduced absenteeism and turnover. Thus, innovative work behaviours not only improve processes and products, but also contribute to a more positive and productive work environment, which supports better business performance.

Overall, the combination of intellectual capital and innovative work behaviour creates synergies that strengthen business performance. Intellectual capital provides the knowledge base and supporting structures, while innovative behaviour leverages that base to create added value. By utilising these two elements effectively, organisations can achieve higher levels of productivity, improve product or service quality, and better respond to market changes, ultimately improving overall business performance. The proper integration of intellectual capital and innovative behaviour is key to achieving sustainable growth and competitive advantage in an increasingly competitive market.

The Impact of Organizational Culture on Business Performance

The research findings indicate that organizational culture has a positive and significant impact on business performance. This conclusion is supported by studies from (Hoiron et al., 2019); (Suripto, 2017); (Odor, 2018); (Carlos Pinho et al., 2014). Organizational culture serves as a crucial foundation for business performance, reflecting the shared values, norms, and beliefs of organizational members. A strong culture can foster an environment that supports productivity, innovation, and employee engagement. For example, a culture that encourages collaboration and open communication can enhance the flow of information and ideas, enabling teams to work more efficiently and respond more swiftly to market changes. Additionally, a culture that values creativity and individual initiative can motivate employees to actively contribute to the development of new products and services, ultimately boosting the business's competitiveness in the market.

In addition to promoting innovation, a positive organizational culture can enhance employee satisfaction and engagement. When employees feel appreciated and

supported by the organization's values, they tend to be more content with their jobs, leading to lower turnover rates and better talent retention. High job satisfaction is often linked to greater productivity, as engaged and motivated employees are more likely to excel in their roles. Thus, fostering and sustaining a positive organizational culture benefits not only the employees but also the overall business performance.

Furthermore, a strong organizational culture can reinforce brand identity and the company's reputation in the eyes of customers and other stakeholders. When a company's values align with the expectations and needs of its customers, stronger and more loyal relationships can be formed. Customers who perceive that they share the same values with the company are likely to be more loyal and more inclined to recommend the company's products or services to others. This can lead to a sustainable increase in market share and revenue.

Therefore, organizational leaders need to actively participate in shaping and maintaining a culture that supports business objectives and employee well-being. This can be achieved through various initiatives such as training and development programs, transparent and open communication, and recognition and rewards for employee achievements. By fostering a positive and inclusive organizational culture, companies can create a work environment that supports superior business performance, ongoing innovation, and high employee satisfaction.

The Impact of Knowledge Management on Business Performance

The analysis results indicate that knowledge management has a positive and significant impact on business performance. These findings align with studies by (Ferdian & Devita, 2020); (Puryantini et al., 2017); (Byukusenge et al., 2016; Byukusenge & Munene, 2017). Effective KM implementation can significantly impact business performance by enabling companies to maximize their intellectual resources, enhance operational efficiency, and drive innovation. Structured and easily accessible knowledge allows employees to make better decisions and respond more effectively to market changes.

KM plays a crucial role in increasing productivity and operational efficiency. With a well-implemented KM system, relevant information can be accessed quickly and easily by employees, thereby significantly reducing the time spent searching for information. Additionally, KM facilitates the dissemination and implementation of best practices throughout the organization. This not only accelerates work processes but also reduces errors and improves the quality of output.

KM also contributes to enhancing innovation and creativity within businesses. By facilitating knowledge sharing and collaboration among employees, KM creates an environment that supports the development of new ideas. Knowledge gathered from various parts of the organization can be combined to create innovative solutions to complex business problems. Furthermore, access to external knowledge, such as industry trends and new technologies, helps companies remain competitive and adaptive to market changes.

With effective KM implementation, companies can improve service quality and customer satisfaction. Up-to-date and accurate information about the company's products and services allows employees to respond quickly and appropriately to customer inquiries and complaints. Additionally, a better understanding of customer

needs and preferences, gained through knowledge management, enables companies to tailor their products and services to better meet customer expectations.

Overall, KM provides a significant competitive advantage for companies. By managing knowledge effectively, companies can continuously enhance their core competencies, which in turn drives long-term business growth. Structured and strategically utilized knowledge allows companies to respond swiftly to market opportunities and address challenges more efficiently. Therefore, effective KM not only contributes to current business performance but also ensures sustainability and growth for the future.

CONCLUSION

This study concludes that there is a significant relationship between intellectual capital, innovative work behavior, organizational culture, and knowledge management with business performance. Intellectual capital serves as a valuable asset that enhances a company's competitiveness and innovation capability. Innovative work behavior drives the development of creative solutions and improves operational efficiency. An organizational culture that supports collaboration and continuous learning creates a productive work environment. KM ensures that relevant knowledge and information are managed and utilized effectively for accurate decision-making. The combination of these four factors collectively contributes to improved business performance, enabling companies to achieve competitive advantage and sustainable growth.

Based on the conclusions of this study, it is recommended that companies increase investment in intellectual capital through training and new technologies to strengthen competitiveness and innovation. Organizations should also encourage innovative work behavior by creating environments that support experimentation and creativity, as well as offering rewards for new ideas. Additionally, it is important to build an organizational culture that fosters collaboration and continuous learning. Knowledge management should be optimized with effective systems for managing and utilizing information. Finally, integrating intellectual capital, innovative behavior, organizational culture, and knowledge management is essential to enhance business performance and achieve competitive advantage and sustainable growth.

Bibliography

- 1) Aida, R. N., & Rahmawati, E. (2015). Pengaruh modal intelektual dan pengungkapannya terhadap nilai perusahaan: Efek intervening kinerja perusahaan. *Journal of Accounting and Investment*, 16(2), 96–109.
- 2) Artati, D. (2017). Pengaruh modal intelektual terhadap kinerja keuangan dan nilai pasar. *Jurnal Ilmiah Akuntansi Dan Keuangan*, 6(1), 59–74.
- 3) Badawi, A. (2018). Pengaruh Good Corporate Governance Dan Intellectual Capital Terhadap Kinerja Keuangan Perusahaan Pada Perbankan Indonesia (Studi Empiris Di Bursa Efek Indonesia Tahun 2015-2017). *Jurnal JDM*, 1(02), 74–86.
- 4) Bella, V., Saroni, P., & Listyaningsih, F. (2023). *Pengaruh Intellectual Capital, Kepemilikan Institusional, Kepemilikan Manajerial Dan Corporate Social Responsibility Terhadap Kinerja Keuangan Perusahaan (Studi Pada Perusahaan Manufaktur Sektor Barang Konsumen Primer yang Terdaftar di Bursa Efek Indonesia Periode 2017-2020)*. 12, 432–449.
- 5) Byukusenge, E., & Munene, J. C. (2017). Knowledge management and business performance: Does innovation matter? *Cogent Business & Management*, 4(1), 1368434.
- 6) Byukusenge, E., Munene, J., & Orobia, L. (2016). *Knowledge management and business performance: Mediating effect of innovation*.

- 7) Cahyaningati, R., Paramita, R. W. D., & Roos Ana, S. (2022). Modal Intelektual, Manajemen Pengetahuan dan Kinerja UMKM serta Kecepatan dan Kualitas Inovasi sebagai Variabel Mediasi. *E-Jurnal Akuntansi*, 32(8).
- 8) Carlos Pinho, J., Paula Rodrigues, A., & Dibb, S. (2014). The role of corporate culture, market orientation and organisational commitment in organisational performance: The case of non-profit organisations. *Journal of Management Development*, 33(4), 374–398.
- 9) Chahal, H., & Bakshi, P. (2014). Effect of intellectual capital on competitive advantage and business performance: Role of innovation and learning culture. *International Journal of Learning and Intellectual Capital*, 11(1), 52–70.
- 10) Darmawan, D., Retnowati, E., Halizah, S. N., Issalillah, F., Khayru, R. K., Hardyansah, R., & Putra, A. R. (2023). Studi Tentang Pengaruh Keunggulan Kompetitif dan Manajemen Sumber Daya Manusia Terhadap Kinerja Perusahaan. *Journal of Management and Economics Research*, 1(3), 77–85.
- 11) Deng, J., Liu, J., Yang, T., & Duan, C. (2022). Behavioural and economic impacts of end-user computing satisfaction: Innovative work behaviour and job performance of employees. *Computers in Human Behavior*, 136, 107367.
- 12) Dewi, N. R., & Setyowati, A. (2015). Analisis pengaruh modal intelektual terhadap kinerja perusahaan. *Fokus Manajerial*, 13(2).
- 13) Elny, S. (2021). Pengaruh perilaku kerja inovatif dan motivasi kerja terhadap kinerja karyawan di cv. enzo Medan. *Wahana Inovasi: Jurnal Penelitian Dan Pengabdian Masyarakat UISU*, 10(2), 362–369.
- 14) Febry, I. H. (2018). Pengaruh modal intelektual terhadap nilai perusahaan dengan kinerja keuangan sebagai variabel intervening. *Jurnal Manajemen Bisnis Indonesia (JMBI)*, 7(3), 284–293.
- 15) Ferdian, A., & Devita, A. R. (2020). Pengaruh Budaya Organisasi Dan Knowledge Management Terhadap Kinerja Karyawan. *Jurnal Penelitian IPTEKS*, 5(2), 187–193.
- 16) Gross-Golacka, E., Kusterka-Jefmańska, M., & Jefmański, B. (2020). Can elements of intellectual capital improve business sustainability?—The perspective of managers of SMEs in Poland. *Sustainability*, 12(4), 1545.
- 17) Hadi, S., Putra, A. R., & Mardikaningsih, R. (2020). Pengaruh perilaku inovatif dan keterlibatan kerja terhadap kinerja karyawan. *Jurnal Baruna Horizon*, 3(1), 186–197.
- 18) Hoiron, M., Wahyudi, E., & Puspitaningtyas, Z. (2019). Pengaruh kapabilitas pemasaran, keunggulan bersaing dan budaya organisasi terhadap kinerja UKM (Usaha Kecil dan Menengah) di Kabupaten Lumajang. *Majalah Ilmiah Dian Ilmu*, 18(1), 37–53.
- 19) Jaradat, Z., AL-Hawamleh, A., Altarawneh, M., Hikal, H., & Elfedawy, A. (2024). The interplay between intellectual capital, business intelligence adoption, and the decision to innovate: Evidence from Jordan. *International Journal of Computing and Digital Systems*, 15(1), 1375–1389.
- 20) Kurniasih, A., & Heliantono. (2016). Intellectual Capital Bank BUMN Terbuka Dan Pengaruhnya Terhadap Kinerja Perusahaan. *Jurnal Ilmiah Manajemen*, VI(2), 195–212.
- 21) Mardikaningsih, R., & Darmawan, D. (2023). Strategi Inovasi Bisnis Sebagai Upaya Peningkatan Keunggulan Kompetitif Dan Pertumbuhan Bisnis UMKM Industri Kreatif Di Era Digital. *Global Leadership Organizational Research in Management*, 1(4), 371–386.
- 22) Mazidah, A., & Laily, N. (2020). Pengaruh knowledge sharing terhadap perilaku inovatif dan kinerja karyawan. *Jurnal Ilmu Dan Riset Manajemen (JIRM)*, 9(2).
- 23) Nugroho, R. (2024). Budaya Organisasi yang Mendorong Inovasi Kerja. *Jurnal Cahaya Mandalika ISSN 2721-4796 (Online)*, 5(2), 882–893.
- 24) Odor, H. O. (2018). Organisational culture and dynamics. *Global Journal of Management and Business Research*, 18(1), 23–29.
- 25) Paramansyah, H. A., & SE, S. H. (2022). *MANAJEMEN STRATEGIS: Strategi, Konsep, & Proses Organisasi*. Almuqstith Pustaka.

- 26) Pigola, A., De Santi, P. V., da Costa, P. R., & Storopoli, J. (2022). Intellectual capital on performance: a meta-analysis study enhancing a new perspective of the components. *Journal of Intellectual Capital*, 23(6), 1379–1403.
- 27) Praharsi, Y. (2016). Manajemen pengetahuan dan implementasinya dalam organisasi dan perorangan. *Jurnal Manajemen Maranatha*, 16(1).
- 28) Puryantini, N., Arfati, R., & Tjahjadi, B. (2017). Pengaruh knowledge management terhadap kinerja organisasi dimediasi inovasi di organisasi penelitian pemerintah. *Berkala Akuntansi Dan Keuangan Indonesia (BAKI)*, 2(2), 21–38.
- 29) Putriana, A. (2023). Analisis Strategi Bisnis di Era Transformasi Digital. *MUKASI: Jurnal Ilmu Komunikasi*, 2(3), 223–232.
- 30) Rochmawati, D. R., Hatimatunnisani, H., & Veranita, M. (2023). *Mengembangkan Strategi Bisnis di Era Transformasi Digital*.
- 31) Rulianti, E. (2022). Pengaruh Komitmen Organisasional, Kepuasan Kerja, dan Budaya Organisasi Terhadap Organizational Citizenship Behavior. *Eqien-Jurnal Ekonomi Dan Bisnis*, 10(1), 341–350.
- 32) Sari, N. P. (2020). Pengaruh modal intelektual terhadap kinerja bisnis pada UKM di Kabupaten Sidoarjo (Studi Empiris pada UKM di Bidang Industri). *Jurnal Akuntansi Unesa*, 8(3), 1–8.
- 33) Suropto, T. (2017). Strategi Meningkatkan Kinerja Perusahaan Melalui Budaya Organisasi Yang Islami. *JESI (Jurnal Ekonomi Syariah Indonesia)*, 6(2), 144–153.
- 34) Sutisna, M. I., Adam, M., & Yunus, M. (2024). *Manajemen dan Organisasi*. Syiah Kuala University Press.
- 35) Tamosiuniene, R., Survilaitė, S., & Shatreovich, V. (2015). Intellectual capital approach to modern management through the perspective of a company's value added. *Business: Theory and Practice*, 16(1), 31–44.
- 36) Taouab, O., & Issor, Z. (2019). Firm performance: Definition and measurement models. *European Scientific Journal*, 15(1), 93–106.
- 37) Vinogradova, T. A., & Kuvshinov, M. S. (2022). The Study Of Employees'innovative Behaviour At Industrial Enterprises. *Journal of New Economy*, 23(3), 109–126.
- 38) Wang, Z., Wang, N., & Liang, H. (2014). Knowledge sharing, intellectual capital and firm performance. *Management Decision*, 52(2), 230–258.